

Computing Minimal Distinguishing Automata in Polynomial Time

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ABSTRACT

We propose a simple and intuitive algorithm for solving md-DFA problem using algorithm concepts within extended operators, our approach shows quadratic polynomial time and hence proves the equivalence between polynomial and non-polynomial classes, we have also shown that minimal non-emptiness of automata problem can be solved in polynomial time with help of modified subset construction, rather than building a product automaton, which leads to factorial size of the memory and time, in this work we also have used many non-tractable existing examples and computed them in polynomial time, which guarantees that our algorithm solves NP-complete problem in almost linear polynomial time, we have also avoided the problem of product automata by an algorithmic approach, we are also giving the starting ground for the proof of back-reference problem which was discussed before, notion of the globally local increment is also given as the main argument towards the resolution of “P versus NP” theorem, which coincides with the finitariness term in general mathematics.

INTRODUCTION

The NP-hardness was first defined in [1], also there’s a defined lower linear bound for deciding arbitrary non-deterministic finite automata on regular languages or even other arbitrary [2]. The problem was first seen on the partial case of non-deterministic automata [3, 4]. The problem of md-DFA is to find a minimal finite automaton which is a subset of any given automata and isn’t included in others [5].

RE-WRITING ALGORITHM

We give the subtraction re-writing method to solve this problem in linear-logarithmic time as per our previous research.

The technique known as re-writing is summarized in table in [7, 8], for the &-operator we use the overridden state with logical consumers as well as for the subtraction operator which is defined within the same terms, however, differing only in logical statement, the complement operator in this manner is also re-written using the alphabet star and subtraction from the operand.

Thus, the mix of re-writing and logical state composition gives the way to the modified subset construction, which rather than visiting every possible composition, produces exact answer on each iteration, thus giving the polynomial running time, rather than exponential or even factorial.

The DFA constructed from the subtraction of DFA_1 and DFA_2 was constructed experimentally on the example in [5].

The first DFA corresponds to the regular expression “((aaaa)*a|(aaaa)*aa|(aaaa)*aaa)”, as the second one to “(a|aa|aaa|aa(aaa)*|aaa(aaa)*)”, the figure above shows the result produced by Regex+ software package [6].

Thus, the decision problems based upon the extended operators can be solved in full and more efficiently if we will choose the strategy of computing locally optimal solution which gives the optimal step to the global one – this technique we will call as the **globally local increment** (GLI). This decision problems which we encountered are only two: minimal distinguishing DFA (md-DFA) and non-emptiness DFA of the given automata – both of which has the state space of factorial size, which, in turn, means that we have to choose the better strategy and solution in order to get to the certificate of acceptance in non-polynomial problem within the visible time limit, in our experiments, it didn’t exceed more than minute.

In the next section we will give the compound benchmarks for the derived examples.

Figure 1. The distinguishing DFA for example in [5].

Figure 2. Example md-DFA for the expression “ $((aaaa)^*a\{1,4\})\{4000\}-(a\{1,3\}(aaa)^*)\{4000\}$ ”.

Re-writing works as it was outlined in [7] and finalized in [8], thus, we can state that the DFA corresponding to the expression $R_1 - R_2$ is a subset of $DFA(R_1)$ and isn't contained in $DFA(R_2)$.

PROOF BY PRODUCT AUTOMATA

As it was presented in [9], the maximal complexity of product construction is the product of its operands, which can be factorial due to the number of automata, however, we can use same methodology as we have presented before using re-writing and event call [7], thus, giving polynomial solution to various number of operands with variable cardinality.

As it was present in [10, 11, 12] the minimal intersection of arbitrary automata cannot be approximated using product construction as it gives the factorial number of solution to be searched, otherwise, the better strategy is to use our approach in [13].

The term “minimal distinguishing” can be also viewed from the approach we invented before as we can compute the minimal possible automaton by simply computing the shortest path between starting and ending points using Dijkstra algorithm.

The non-emptiness problem which is known to be NP-hard will be also proved to be solvable by a polynomial algorithm in the next section.

Another counter-example is from [14], where the expression in the form “(ab)*&...” was studied, we have shown in the next section that it can be computed in time of several seconds for the string of length 8000 containing 1000 intersection expressions – this gives the contrary towards the minimal DFA recognizing this language which has an exponential complexity.

During the review of the present results we haven’t met other counter examples which could get the running experimental program to work with errors or in not observable time frame.

Another case we get from [15] for intersection operator, which gives the exponential estimation of the time and space complexity, our results give the reasonable amount of time not greater than 12 seconds for one thousand intersections.

The proof of correctness of re-writing algorithm and modified subset construction can be found in [16], as it was presented much more earlier.

We also point the regression of complexity to almost linear and quadratic with respect to the back-referencing problem in extended regular expressions, as it was stated before in [17], one can see that number of decompositions decreases as we proceed further with the given search and, thus, certificate of acceptance is achieved almost “on the fly”.

The co-NP complete problem [18] can be by analogy solved in reasonable time as of our experimentation procedure, which states that co-NP classes lie within polynomial P classes.

BENCHMARKS & EXPERIMENTATION

Below is a summary of the tests on the expression in the form of $((a^k)^* a^{1..k})^k - (a^{1..k} (a^k)^*)^k$:

Table 1. The results of expression tests using re-writing algorithm

k	String length	DFA Number of States	Time (sec)
0	63	16	0.155
1	93	25	0.018
2	129	36	0.032
3	171	49	0.042
4	219	64	0.053
5	273	81	0.071
6	333	100	0.085
7	399	121	0.093
8	471	144	0.185
9	549	169	0.261
10	633	196	0.817

11	723	225	0.403
12	819	256	0.389
13	921	289	0.509
20	1803	576	2.808
30	3573	1156	13.06
40	5943	1936	41.488
50	8913	2916	188.674
60	12483	4096	276.88
70	16653	5476	585.398
80	21423	7056	1222.708

Below is a visualization of the data in Table 1, as it can be seen results converge to quadratic polynomial function.

Figure 3. Visualization of the benchmarks in Table 2.

With respect to the term fixed-parameter tractability (FPT) as our alphabet before in tests consisted of only letter 'a', we have run tests for arbitrary alphabet "abcd" for cases in form $((a|b|c|d)^*)^k(a|b|c|d)^k - ((a|b|c|d)^k((a|b|c|d)^*)^k)$:

Table 2. Tests for the quadratic alphabet.

k	String length	DFA Number of States	Time (sec)
0	104	14	0.284
1	158	12	0.08
2	224	13	0.059
3	302	14	0.1
4	392	15	0.132
5	494	16	0.131

6	608	17	0.209
7	734	18	0.307
8	872	19	0.335
9	1022	20	0.338
10	1184	21	0.437
11	1358	22	0.394
12	1544	23	0.423
13	1742	24	0.529
20	3464	31	1.78
30	6944	41	7.442
40	11624	51	17.878

Figure 4. Visualization for example arbitrary alphabet.

In the next table we will use the regular expression in the form “a^k*&..”, k = 1..n, the results are as follows:

Table 3. Results for non-emptiness test

String length	DFA Number of States	Time (sec)
6	2	0.135
13	2	0.008
14	3	0.005
21	3	0.009
22	3	0.004
23	7	0.007
30	7	0.008
31	7	0.006
32	7	0.009

33	13	0.006
40	13	0.011
41	13	0.014
42	13	0.013
55	61	0.016
77	421	0.197
93	841	1.003
109	2521	6.094
125	2521	5.678

Figure 5. The visualization of the performance of the non-emptiness test algorithm.

Figure 6. The non-emptiness DFA for the expression “((a)*)&((aa)*)&((aaa)*)&((aaaa)*)&((aaa)*)”.

Figure 7. The resulting DFAs for expressions “((ab)*)&...” and “(a*a)&...”

CONCLUSION

We have given a fully polynomial algorithm for the md-DFA problem which is NP-complete = this fact gives the experimental proof of the equivalence of complexity classes like polynomial “P” and non-polynomial “NP” as the benchmarks above state as the argument as they are almost linear to the size of the expressions and running time depends also linearly, also, the problem described was proved to be NP-complete before.

We have also shown the experimental proof of tractability of the problems like md-DFA and Non-emptiness-DFA which are known to lie in NP-class of complexity.

We have also concluded that within the new proof, back-referencing problem can be computed fast within arbitrary number of capturing groups.

Thus, we claim experimental proof of “P versus NP” theorem: $P = NP$, which could be used in solving other problems like Rhiemann hypothesis by Akram Louiz [19].

The reader is invited to use Regex+ software package and provide examples.

I also have some notes about theories like fixed-parameter tractability and classification – all these theories and similar to them are all about the direct solution or final resolution of P-NP theorem by Cook, while our conjecture [20] gives the final outcome with respect to the full statement of the problem: are there solution to NP-complete problem or not.

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